

FIGHTING CORRUPTION. CONCEPT AND TYPES OF CORRUPTION

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Abstract. *The article is aimed to analyze the concept and type of corruption, various types of corruption and their meanings are described. It helps to identify specific types of corruption, its consequences and the impact it has on society. The article provides information on scientific and practical approaches to combating corruption, examining the positions of corruption in physical, spiritual or other spheres, and reflecting various importances against it.*

Keywords: *corruption, permission, last, article, court, international, organization, role, legal, offer.*

The concept and category of corruption is generally understood in a wide range of areas such as economy, politics, law and other fields. Corruption is a bad practice among security and development hunters, changers and others. These types of activities can be spectacular, small, or high-level, and can be done in the form of cash, supervision, or other extraordinary benefits. In order to prevent corruption, it is necessary to strengthen the legal, social and political structures, improve transparency.

Building a free civil society in a democratic state is a complex and multi-systemic issue with its own challenges. In this way, the state relies on democratic principles, universally recognized principles and legal frameworks. It serves as a basis not only for the socio-economic development of the society, but also for resisting the forces that destroy the democratic system and block development. Democracy, that is, the construction of people's power, every state that raises the level of "the people as the only source of power" opposes the destructive ideas and the factors that serve them. One such factor is corruption. Corruption is a complex social phenomenon that originated in ancient times and exists today in almost all countries of the world, acting as a factor with its various forms and manifestations. Corruption (lat.corruptio) means "bribery of public and political figures, state officials. In another sense (lat.corruptio) – bribing someone with money or other material resources". If we turn to the history of the states of the ancient world, we see that the definition of "corruptio" in Roman law was interpreted in the most general sense as "to damage, destroy, bribe" and in judicial practice it meant illegal actions. This concept comes from the combination of the Latin words "correi" "several participants of one of the parties to the relationship of obligation on the same subject" and "rumpere" "to break, destroy, cancel", more precisely, this concept is an independent judicial process in Ancient Rome, it refers to the process of participation in the activities of several (at least two) persons, which consists in harming the normal process of the court or the process of managing public affairs" [1].

As a result of the analysis, the following features characteristic of the corruption phenomenon can be distinguished:

Corruption is not a mechanical simple collection of the same crimes, but a complex social and legal phenomenon;

Corruption is a systemic phenomenon, so a one-time bribe to a civil servant is not considered corruption;

Corruption is the regular receipt of material and other benefits from third parties (groups) by public servants for their own benefit, etc. [2].

Russian researcher V.V. Luneev considers corruption “a socio-legal or criminological phenomenon covering a set of socially dangerous actions recognized as criminal in world practice” [3]. Another scientist P.A. Cheboksarov defines corruption as “a set of negative events occurring in society and the state” [4] and A.V. Kuzmin of corruption in our current society states that there are two types: narrow and broad understanding [5].

At the moment, comprehensive measures to fight against corruption have been developed in the Republic of Uzbekistan. And it occupies a leading position in the world. Corruption permeates all levels of society and causes irreparable damage to the country. This phenomenon did not appear yesterday and poses a serious threat.

On January 3, 2017, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption”[6] opened a new page in this field. This legal document has the following specific features. First, it specifies the bodies and organizations that implement and participate in anti-corruption activities. And the systematic work in this field helps to organize anti-corruption work as a system. Secondly, one of the important features is that the issue of raising legal awareness and legal culture in the field of combating corruption was specifically addressed within the framework of the law, and the factors of its organization and implementation mechanisms were determined. Third, the law on measures to prevent corruption it is a feature that is specified in the document, and the specified measures are not only the fight against corruption with legislation and sanctions, but prevention, and for this, raising the legal consciousness and culture of the citizen at the same time. The factor that creates all the conditions for organizing a corruption-free life in society is widely discussed.

Fourthly, detection of corruption offenses, putting an end to them, the inevitability of responsibility, which is the most basic element of the system of a legal democratic society, the imperative features of the laws, and the mandatory punishment for the committed act, in this regard various principles and specifics of the movement are discussed. In general, this law plays an important role in the formation of our citizens’ New Uzbekistan, which is expressed in our national ideal, our noblest goals.

A deep study of the impact of corruption on the democratic system and civil society reveals once again the importance of applying every principle and measure given in the law. The impact of corruption in society is so great that it reduces the efficiency of the market economy, reduces the effectiveness of the existing democratic institutions, leads to a decrease and loss of people’s trust in the government, and increases political and economic inequality. In addition, it can cause organized crime and threaten the national security of the country.

Today, corruption has penetrated into all areas of our social life. In order to more fully understand the meaning of corruption in the state system, it is necessary to formulate a definition of this concept. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption”, corruption means “illegal use of one’s position or service position by a person for the purpose of obtaining material or immaterial benefits for personal interests or the interests of other persons, as well as the understanding of providing such a name against the law”. The effectiveness of the anti-corruption system largely depends on understanding the economic, political, legal and

psychological factors that cause corruption. There are economic, political, legal, and psychological factors of the emergence of corruption and its penetration into the social life of the society. For example, economic factors include:

Increased inflation, which means economic instability, which is manifested in the high level of depreciation of the salaries of civil servants, which encourages them to look for any other sources of income;

Dissatisfaction with the conditions of payment of wages, which means that people are dissatisfied with the procedure, incentive system and general economic factors of organizing the activities of employees. This gradually creates a mood of deviance in the employee. Also, the analysis of political factors is important in the legal development of the system of fighting against corruption. The main factors are: lack of effective control over employees' incomes and expenses, the performance of their duties, non-compliance with the requirements of the anti-corruption system, or the fact that they are in a weak position that is not based on the law. This, in turn, leads to negative changes in all relationships in society, affecting internal subsystems through management.

In conclusion, we can say that it is clear from the analysis and methodological observations that studying the nature of corruption and approaches to understanding its structure will help to develop effective measures to fight against corruption and ultimately ensure the strengthening of legality and discipline in public administration. For this, it will be necessary to carry out extensive scientific research, to develop mechanisms to further increase the effectiveness of the measures being taken to prevent the spread of this disease, which is seen as a barrier to our development.

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